

THE IMPORTANCE OF LICORICE IN OUR LIVES

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Abstract: Licorice is used in several industries. Licorice root also has several medicinal properties, it is used to treat almost all types of lung, liver, circulatory and kidney diseases. Licorice is also an ingredient in some topical (skin application) products. Certain products containing licorice root and other ingredients can help relieve indigestion. While licorice has a number of beneficial properties, it also has some of its own side effects. Licorice is thought to derive from a component called glycyrrhizic acid. that is, diomo may not have useful features. We will provide similar useful information in this article.

Key words: Legumes, medicinal properties, side effects, botanical description, life form.

Абстрактный: Солодка используется в различных областях. Корень солодки также обладает рядом лечебных свойств, его применяют при лечении практически всех видов заболеваний легких, печени, кровообращения и почек. Солодка также входит в состав некоторых продуктов местного применения (наносимых на кожу). Некоторые продукты, содержащие корень солодки и другие ингредиенты, могут помочь облегчить расстройство желудка. Хотя солодка обладает рядом полезных свойств, она также имеет и свои побочные эффекты. Считается, что солодка состоит из компонента, называемого глицирризиновой кислотой, то есть диомо может не иметь полезных свойств. Вот такую полезную информацию мы предоставим в этой статье.

Ключевые слова: Бобовые культуры, лечебные свойства, побочные эффекты, ботаническое описание, жизненная форма.

Introduction

Today, great attention is being paid to turning our country into a green space and increasing the varieties of medicinal plants. The organization of cultivating medicinal plants in a cultural manner and processing them, supporting the establishment of cultural plantations of medicinal plants, and widely using medicinal plants for the prevention and treatment of diseases are some of the measures being taken by our president through various decisions. Nature has always been a wonderful source of therapeutic substances, providing us with various medicinal plants that produce

valuable phytochemicals. Licorice, scientifically known as *Glycyrrhiza*, belongs to the Leguminosae family and is a frequently used herb. This medicinal plant is found throughout Asia as well as Europe. Licorice is believed to have originated in Iraq. It is widely distributed in Italy, Spain, Turkey, the Caucasus, Western China, and Central Asia. In contrast, licorice is commercially cultivated in Central Asia, China, Mongolia, Italy, Spain, Greece, France, Iran, Iraq, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Syria, Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, India, China, the USA, and England.

Licorice has a long history that spans thousands of years. Evidence of the plant has been found in ancient Egyptian, Chinese, Greek, Roman, and Hindu civilizations, and it is said that many famous historical figures used licorice for its medicinal properties. These include King Tut, Alexander the Great, Julius Caesar, and Napoleon Bonaparte, who reportedly consumed it so frequently that his teeth were stained black from the juice! One interesting fact is that licorice candy originally got its name from the licorice plant, an herbaceous shrub with many imitators. The most common imitator of licorice in food and confectionery is anise, with Greek liqueur Ouzo resembling licorice. Before its use in confectionery, licorice was primarily used as an ingredient to sweeten bread and cakes, and it was even added to beer. In the 17th century, licorice candy, as we know it, first appeared in the Netherlands. Licorice root is well-suited for use in confectionery because it contains glycyrrhizin, a compound that is 30-50 times sweeter than sugar! By the early 20th century, licorice candy was a popular treat available in various shapes, such as pipes, golf clubs, and cigarettes. There are two main methods for making licorice sweets. Some companies use a molding process where liquid licorice mixture is poured into separate molds. Once cooled, the candies are removed from the molds and prepared for packaging. Another method for producing licorice candy is extrusion, which is used to create licorice ropes and laces. In this process, the ingredients are boiled until the mixture reaches the consistency of dough, and then it is extruded through forming machines that shape the candy.

Main Body: Licorice first became famous for its medicinal properties. When chewed, the root not only helps provide hydration but also contains important juices that help relieve mild inflammation, chest congestion, and allergies. Alexander the Great instructed his soldiers to chew the roots to stay healthy and hydrated, and during the Middle Ages, no Italian pharmacy worth its salt would be caught without a supply of licorice. And they were not mistaken! Modern medical research has confirmed that licorice can soothe the stomach and clear the respiratory system.

Licorice requires deep, well-cultivated, fertile soil that retains moisture well to produce good roots. It prefers sandy soil with ample moisture and does not thrive in clay. Light alkaline conditions produce the best plants. Licorice can withstand strong winds but does not tolerate salty coastal winds or clay soils. Initially, plants grow slowly, but once established, the species can become weedy and difficult to remove if not controlled with regular harvesting.

Licorice is one of the most valuable plants worldwide and is widely used in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals. It is utilized as a flavoring agent in sweets, other foods, beverages, and tobacco products. Licorice root is cultivated throughout Europe, Asia, and the Middle East. Many "licorice" products sold in the United States do not contain real licorice. Instead, anise oil, which has a similar smell and taste to licorice, is often used. Licorice root has a long history that dates back to the ancient civilizations of Assyria, Egypt, China, and India. Traditionally, it has been used to treat a variety of conditions, including lung, liver, circulatory, and kidney diseases.

Licorice has been thoroughly studied in phytochemical and pharmaceutical analyses. In traditional Chinese medicine (TCM), *Glycyrrhiza glabra* is considered a "fundamental herbal medicine." According to TCM beliefs, "nine out of ten formulas include licorice," and it is one of the most effective herbal medicines for reducing toxicity and enhancing the effectiveness of other herbal remedies when used together. There are approximately 30 species of licorice. Licorice is one of the most widely used species in nutrition and food. It contains amino acids, proteins, simple sugars, polysaccharides, mineral salts, pectins, starches, sterols, gums, and resins. Licorice roots produce a potent sweet compound used in teas and candies. For centuries, it has been a source of glycerin and a component in traditional medicine. The sweet compound, glycyrrhizin, is 50-170 times sweeter than sugar (sucrose). The extract possesses antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antimutagenic properties. The earliest records of using this plant's medicinal properties date back to

2100 BCE. Licorice is also beneficial for treating atopic dermatitis, a chronic condition known as eczema, characterized by skin irritation, inflammation, and itching.

Research shows that rinsing medical instruments with licorice or using licorice lozenges before surgery can help prevent or reduce the common postoperative sore throat. Licorice has the ability to inhibit melanin pigment production, which can help lighten skin spots and even out the overall skin tone. Additionally, due to its anti-inflammatory properties, licorice extract can reduce redness and swelling associated with post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation. Licorice extract acts as a natural pigment inhibitor, helping to lighten dark spots and patches on the skin.

Various painful internal ulcers caused by *H. pylori* bacteria develop in the stomach, lower esophagus, or small intestine. Licorice flavonoid helps alleviate stomach ulcers by increasing mucus production, reducing inflammation, and improving the gut microbiome.

Licorice also promotes hair growth by improving blood flow to the scalp, thereby accelerating hair growth. It can play a moisturizing role, helping to hydrate the scalp for healthy hair growth.

Furthermore, licorice has properties that can help alleviate amnesia (a memory disorder characterized by the inability to recall past events and experiences, or only partially recalling them).

Licorice reduces body fat and controls aldosterone levels, both of which are responsible for weight gain. Rich in plant-based chemicals that act as antioxidants,

licorice oil helps people lose weight by controlling an enzyme involved in fat accumulation and breakdown in the body. Licorice has amazed us with its sweetness and medicinal properties, but it also has other interesting and useful characteristics. Before modern methods, water purified with licorice extract was used to extinguish fires. Even the remnants of licorice roots, after extracting other beneficial parts, are sturdy and were often used to make boards for boxes.

You might not have known that this classic food has been enjoyed for thousands of years due to its many properties. Its qualities have been revered by Buddhist monks, Greek philosophers, war heroes, and more recently, medical professionals. From its roots in medicine to sweet cakes and the black licorice candies we know today, the history of licorice and licorice candy is truly fascinating.

Products containing licorice should be labeled. Manufacturers indicate licorice extract or glycyrrhizic acid in the ingredient list. According to the WHO, up to 100 mg of glycyrrhizic acid per day, roughly equivalent to 60-70 grams of licorice, is safe for most adults.

Consumption in high doses is considered toxic. Before using licorice extract in products, most of the problematic component, glycyrrhizin, is removed to retain enough flavor while reducing toxicity. Excessive consumption of licorice during pregnancy is associated with preterm birth and health issues in the child. There is limited information on the safety of using licorice root during breastfeeding.

Conclusion: We can use various medicinal plants to prevent many of our illnesses. However, due to our misuse of nature, their numbers are decreasing year by year. These medicinal plants play an important role in our lives, so we need to protect and increase their numbers.

Using these plants not only for treating diseases but also for preventing them is more beneficial. However, people usually do not see a doctor until the illness shows its effects (i.e., their condition worsens). If we regularly visit the doctor and take preventive measures with natural remedies when the initial signs of disease are detected, we can maintain our health and avoid being troubled by any illnesses.

Among medicinal plants, licorice holds a primary position due to its medicinal properties. When consumed raw, licorice root strengthens the spleen, reduces body temperature, and eliminates toxins. The root tips help relieve pain and infections in the urinary tract. When cooked, licorice root aids in cleansing the spleen, stomach, and digestive system, helping to alleviate diarrhea, cough, shortness of breath, and energy deficiency by strengthening the spleen.

Licorice root, in combination with white peony root (*Paeoniae radix alba* or *bai shao*), can also help reduce cramps and relieve pain in the abdominal and leg muscles.

References:

1. Kuriyama A, Maeda H. [Kattalardagi operatsiyadan keyingi tomoq og'rig'ining oldini olish uchun qizilmiyaning dolzarb qo'llanilishi: tizimli ko'rib chiqish va meta-tahlil.](#) *Klinik anesteziya jurnali*. 2019;54:25-32.
2. Qizilmiya. Tabiiy dorilar veb-sayti. 2020-yil 5-martda naturalmedicines.therapeuticresearch.com saytiga kirilgan. [Ma'lumotlar bazasi obunasi].
3. Burxon, F., & Dilshod, M. (2023). ZARAFSHON VOHASI SHAROITIDA TERAQ BARGXO 'RI CHRYSOMELA POPULI L. NING BIOLOGIK-EKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA ZARARI. PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION, 19(23), 411-414.
4. Нуриллаев, Ж. Я., Нуриллаев, Х. Ж., Бердимуродова, Ф. П., & Мухамадиев, Н. К. (2023). ОЦЕНКА ЛЕЧЕБНЫХ И МЕТАФИЛАКТИЧЕСКИХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ ПРИ МОЧЕКАМЕННОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ В ЗАВИСИМОСТИ ОТ СОСТАВА КАМНЯ. *Медицинский вестник Башкортостана*, 18(1 (103)), 24-28.
5. Nazari S, Rameshrad M, Hosseinzadeh H. [Glycyrrhiza glabra ning toksikologik ta'siri \(qizilmiya\): sharh.](#) *Fitoterapiya tadqiqotlari h*. 2017;31(11):1635-1650.
6. Нуриллаев, Ж. Я., & Мухамадиев, Н. К. (2007). Особенности липидного обмена у больных с пузырно-влагалищными свищами. *Урология*, (6), 36-39.
7. Burxon, F., Enverovna, B. L., & Dilshod, M. (2024). CHAKANDA (HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES) DORIVOR O'SIMLIGINING ZARARKUNANDALARI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 21), 733-737.
8. Нуриллаев, Ж. Я. (1999). Оценка метафилактических мероприятий по отдаленным результатам хирургического лечения мочекаменной болезни у детей.
9. Батиров, Х. Ф., Файзуллаев, Б., & Маликов, Д. (2022). ЗИМУЮЩИЕ ДВУЛЕТНИКИ В КАЧЕСТВЕ СИДЕРАТОВ. кандидат физико-математических наук, доцент ТН Ледащева Ч л е н ы р е д к о л л е г и и: доктор экономических наук, профессор ММ Редина; доктор геолого-минералдогических наук, профессор АП Хаустов; кандидат технических наук, профессор ЕВ Станис, 21, 311.

10. Ruzikulova, D., & Muminov, D. (2022). INSURANCE TECHNICAL RISKS AND CHALLENGES OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT. *Women's Health Medicine*, 18(1).
11. Nurillaev, J. Y. (2024). Theoretical and methodological foundations of financing karakul farming in a market economy.
12. Khasanova, F. (2023). History of The Formation of Baihua. *Spast Abstracts*, 2(02).
13. Nurillaev, J. Y. . (2021). Directions To Improve The Activities Of The Karakulchil Sector In Uzbekistan. *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research*, 3(02), 57–62.
<https://doi.org/10.37547/tajjir/Volume03Issue02-11>
14. Karimov, A., & Khasanova, F. The Impact of Ancient Chinese on Baihua Language.
15. Khasanova, F. (2022). The Formation and Formation of The Chinese Language Baihua as The Basis of The Modern Chinese Language. *Sharq Mash'ali*, (01), 21-23.
16. Nurillayev, J. Y. (2022). The role of corporate management system in providing financial security in commercial banks.
17. Yarashevich, P. N. J. (2023). Factors for Choosing a Marketing Strategy in Tourism Development.